

LI-FI Communication Systems: Prospects & Challenges

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Abstract—*Light Fidelity (Li-Fi) is a wireless optical networking technology that uses light-emitting diodes (LEDs) for data transmission. Li-Fi is designed for data transfer system by using LED light bulbs similar to those are currently in used in many energy-conscious home and offices. However, Li-Fi is a wireless technology that holds the key to solve upcoming challenges faced by 5th Generation (5G) technology. This technology can transmit data at multiple gigabits, is more authenticated, virtually interference free and uniquely more secure than radio technology such as Wi-Fi or cellular. Due to the latest improvements, it has become a reliable alternative solution of forthcoming radio frequency RF spectrum crisis, especially in certain places and situations. Li-Fi, which is related to Visible Light Communication (VLC) is going to be the latest and fastest data communication technology in near future.*

Index Terms— Li-Fi, Light Wave, Optical Communication, Fiber Optics.

I. INTRODUCTION

LIGHT Fidelity could be a bi-directional high-speed and totally networked wireless communication technology. It works by transmitting data through illumination by sending the data through an LED light bulb. When an electrical current is applied to an LED light bulb [1, 2], a stream of light is emitted from the bulb. LED bulbs are semiconductor devices. That means the brightness of the light flowing through them can be changed at extremely high speeds. This allows anyone to send a signal by modulating the light at different rates.

Li-Fi is like Wi-Fi. But efficiency and safety of the internet are the dominating issues right now. The performance of Li-Fi is way better than the performance of Wi-Fi. The speed of Li-Fi is thousand times faster than Wi-Fi. Li-Fi is more secure than Wi-Fi based on the spread of the signal. Li-Fi cannot work through the walls. The vulnerability exists if there is any leakage in the wall while having an indoor communication [3]. Li-Fi uses LED light bulbs to enable data transfer, boasting speeds of up to 224 gigabits per second. Li-Fi was coined by Dr Harald Haas during a TED talk in 2011 who is a professor of The University of Edinburgh. Li-Fi can be implemented for making smart homes especially for elderly care to monitor

their health and to make their life easier. Li-Fi can also be used in medical care, aircraft, library, traffic control management and for road safety [4-7]. Li-Fi works with light. This technology can be enabled to dim low enough that a room will appear dark and still transmits data. So Li-Fi is a continuation of the trend to move to higher frequencies in the electromagnetic spectrum.

II. WORKING OF LI-FI

A. Basic Concept

Light Fidelity (Li-Fi) technology may be wireless communications system supported the utilization of visible radiation between the violet (800 THz) and red (400THz). Not like Wi-Fi that uses the radio a part of the spectrum, Li-Fi uses the optical spectrum i.e. visible radiation a part of the spectrum. The principle of Li-Fi is predicated on causation knowledge by AM of the sunshine supply in an exceedingly well-defined and standardized means. LEDs are often switched on and off quicker than human eyes will sight since the in the operation speed of LEDs is a smaller amount than one-time unit. This invisible on-off activity permits knowledge transmission victimization binary codes. If the junction rectifier is on, a digital '1' is transmitted and if the junction rectifier is off, a digital '0' is transmitted. Additionally, these junction rectifiers are often switched on and off terribly quickly which provides U.S. an awfully nice chance for transmittal knowledge lead lights, as a result of there aren't any officious light-weight frequencies like that of the radio frequencies in Wi-Fi. Li-Fi is believed to be eightieth a lot of economical [8], which implies it will reach speeds of up to 1Gbps and even in the far side. Li-Fi differs from fiber optic as a result of the Li-Fi protocol layers square measure appropriate for wireless communication over short distances (up to ten meters). Five This puts Li-Fi in an exceedingly distinctive position of very quick wireless communication over short distances.

B. Propagation of Li-Fi

The operating of Li-Fi is incredibly straightforward. There's a light-weight electrode on one finish i.e. A diode transmitter, and a photograph detector (light sensor) on the opposite. The information input to the diode transmitter is encoded into the sunshine (technically spoken as Actinic ray Communication) by varied the flicker rate at that the LEDs flicker 'on' and 'off' to come up with totally different strings of 1s and 0s [8]. The on/off activity of the diode transmitter that appears to be invisible (The diode intensity is modulated so chop-chop that human eye cannot notice, therefore the lightweight of the

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diode seems constant to humans), enables information transmission in lightweight kind in accordance with incoming binary codes: switch ON a diode could be a logical '1', switch it OFF could be a logical '0' [9]. By varied the speed at that the LEDs flicker on and off, data may be encoded within the lightweight to totally different mixtures of 1s and 0s.

C. Communication Type

The frequency spectrum that's accessible to USA within the atmosphere consists of many wave regions like X-rays, gamma rays, u-v region, infrared region, actinic radiation rays, radio waves, etc. Any one of the on top of waves are often employed in the approaching communication technologies. However, why the Visible Light half is chosen? The rationale behind this can be the straightforward accessibility and lesser harmful effects that occur thanks to these rays of sunshine. VLC uses the actinic radiation between four hundred rate (780nm) and 800 rate (375 nm) as medium that is less dangerous for high-voltage applications, and conjointly humans will simply understand it and defend themselves from the harmful effects whereas the other wave regions have following disadvantages:- Radio waves are dearly-won (due to spectrum charges) and fewer secure (due to interference and attainable interception, etc.) Gamma rays are harmful as a result, it may be dangerous addressing it, by the kinsmen. Thanks to their tried adverse effects on human health. X-rays have health problems, almost like the Gamma Rays. Ultraviolet radiation is often thought about for communication technology functions at place without individuals, otherwise they will even be dangerous for the same once exposed incessantly [10]. Infrared, thanks to high safety regulation, will solely be used with low power. Thence the actinic radiation portion (from red to blue) of the spectrum doesn't cause any hurt to the individuals as visible rays are safe to use, give larger information measure and conjointly have a promising future within the communication field.

III. LI-FI AND WI-FI

Both Wi-Fi and Li-Fi will offer wireless net access to users, and each the technologies transmit information over spectrum. Li-Fi could be an actinic ray communication technology useful to get high-speed wireless communication. The distinction is: Wi-Fi technology uses radio waves for transmission, whereas Li-Fi utilizes light-weight waves. Wi-Fi works well for general wireless coverage at intervals building/campus/compound, and Li-Fi is right for top density wireless information coverage within a confined space or space and is free from interference problems in contrast to the Wi-Fi. Table 1 shows a comparison of transfer speed of assorted wireless technologies. Table 2 showed a comparison of Li-Fi with Wi-Fi.

Table 1: Comparison of speed of various wireless technologies [1, 5-8]

Technology	Speed
Li-Fi	~ 1 Gbps
Wi-fi – IEEE 802.11n	~ 150 Mbps
IrDA	~ 4 Mbps
Bluetooth	~ 3 Mbps
NFC	~ 424 Kbps

Table 2: Comparison of Wi-Fi and Li-Fi [2-5]

Parameter	Li-Fi	Wi-Fi
Spectrum Used	Visible Light	RF
Standard	IEEE 802.15.7	IEEE 802.11
Range	Based on Light Intensity (< 10m)	Based on Radio propagation & interference (<300 m)
Data Transfer Rate	Very high (~ 1Gbps)	Low (100 Mbps -1 Gbps)
Power Consumption	Low	High
Cost	Low	High
Bandwidth	Unlimited	Limited

IV. SCOPES AND HINDRANCE

Scope

- Li-Fi requires Line of sight.
- If the apparatus is set up outdoor, it would need to deal with changing weather conditions.
- If the apparatus is set up indoors, one would not be able to shift the receiver.
- The problem of how the receiver will transmit back to the transmitter persists.
- Light waves can easily be blocked and can't penetrate thick walls as the radio waves can.

Limitations

The technology is based on visible light communication which uses visible light for data communication. VLS, we used a source of illumination which cannot only produce illumination but also send information using the same light. So, we can say that VLS [11] is illumination along with communication. Now, suppose we switch the torch ON and OFF state, the torch appears to be ON constantly, and additional, we also cannot see the data transmitted. We would, of course, need a receiver. Unlike Wi-Fi technology, Li-Fi cannot travel through non-transport material, such as walls, which will provide more secure data transfer as it confines the data transmission to one area, and it does not have any interference issue. The use of LED lightweight in Li-Fi, makes it additional appropriate for indoor applications as a result of it's cheaper and safer for eyes. As a security system in our proposed smart home, we suggest the use of a WWSN that consists of many tiny visual sensor nodes called camera nodes, which integrate an image sensor, an embedded processor, and wireless transceiver.

V. IDENTIFIED PROBLEMS WITH SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS

Problem- 1: Li-Fi transmitters use solid-state LEDs integrated/embedded with controllers that receive data and modulate the light output of LED according to bits of data. The lighting devices are generally phosphor based or RGB lightings and both has their own set of strengths and weaknesses. Phosphor based light sources are cheaper in cost as compared to RGB based devices, but they provide less bandwidth than RGB sources due to their low switching

speed. This isn't a big problem, however. One of the major financial hurdles in Li-Fi is as follow:

Consider a scenario where to implement Li-Fi at a location pre-installed with lighting fixtures. There seem to be two options:

1. replace the existing light source with a new one that contains integrated VLC modulation controller; or
2. fix a new VLC enabled light source

None of the options above however solves the cost issue in Li-Fi and do not offer any cost savings.

Solution 1: Introducing A Modulating Element

There are found two patents on Li-Fi – WO2017042093A1 and EP3139524A1 – where inventors introduced a new modulating element. This element, when attached to the existing light source, has the capability to modulate the existing light output based on the data that needs to be transmitted. More precisely, the modulator selectively changes the transmission or reflection of the light in response to the data to be transmitted and thereby converting the existing normal light fixtures into Li-Fi transmitter. Thus, the need of changing the light fixture gets eliminated.

Fig. 1: EP3139524A1 Li-Fi.

In existing systems, to create coded light, the light is modulated by modulating the amount of light emitted by the light source. However, it is recognized herein that this is not the only possible way to achieve coded light. For instance, it may be desirable to be able to embed data in the light from pre-existing or naturally occurring light sources whereby the emitted light itself cannot be modulated at the point of emission.

Fig. 2: Data Transmission of Li-Fi system.

Solution 2: Adding an Add-On Controller to make existing light sources Li-Fi compatible

There is found another patent in which, an **add-on controller** is used as a standalone component, which can be attached to the pre-existing light source.

Fig. 3: Li-Fi add-on controller [12].

The controller can work as back-end modulator and direct the light source to emit a light of intensity/power by modifying the power input.

The controller contains,

- a data signal receiver that is configured to receive data from the external data source,
- a VLC protocol engine configured for interpreting the received data according to VLC protocol, and
- a VLC transceiver for converting the received data into one or more LIBM (Light Intensity Baseband Modulation) modulated signals.

The control unit then activates and deactivates its power output port to supply output voltage responsive to the one or more LIBM-modulated signals and controls the light source output.

Fig. 4: Suggested Li-Fi implementation system.

Problem-2:

A great problem with the Li-Fi technology is that the light needs to be on all the time, even during night.

Solution:

In this nonstop networking system, it may be used IR (Infrared Radiation) bulb instead of LED (Light-Emitting Diode) bulb. When turn off LED bulb switch from switchboard signal does not go direct LED bulb. First signal pass through Arduino and Arduino will turn off the LED lights slowly. In the mine time LDR(Light Dependent Resistor) sensor senses dark mode and the signal will be pass throw,

Arduino. At a time, Arduino will automatically turn on the IR bulb. In this process, our networking system will continue.

I. CONCLUSION

Li-Fi is becoming more suitable networks for the next generation of health service at the hospital. In these documents, the applications of VLC are demonstrated in HMS using a prototype model. The Li-Fi network can be successfully used at a high-speed. The use of this technology in the field of medicine makes a faster diagnosis and allows you to access the internet with the radio wave-based apparatus. The proposed system is completely automated, and this could be a milestone in the medical field if it is implemented successfully.

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